

Solutions to Complete the Equipment Tuna Supply Chain to Japan

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Abstract:

The article introduced the current status of the tuna supply chain to the Japanese market. Since then, the author analyzes and recommends solutions to complete the tuna supply chain to the Japanese market. Solutions proposed for fishing businesses, tuna processing businesses and solutions to the authorities and the Vietnam Fisheries Association.

Keywords: Tuna supply chain, Vietnam - Japan

1. Introduction

For Vietnam, for many years, seafood has always been the main export product. In particular, tuna is considered one of the commodities with great potentials and advantages, because our country has more than 1 million km² of exclusive economic waters. However, the current status of Vietnam's tuna exports is not commensurate with the potential, especially with the Japanese market. This is a large-capacity market, Vietnam - Japan also signed free trade agreements VJEP, AJCEP and CPTPP. However, Vietnamese tuna products only account for a small market share in this market. The reason for this limitation is that the supply chain of Vietnamese tuna products to the Japanese market is not appropriate, and has not yet linked Vietnamese producers with Japanese customers.

In practical terms, the competitive advantage of enterprises in the globalization trend, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises will not only depend on the capacity of each enterprise, but increasingly depends more on the association, cooperation with other businesses in a value chain, product supply chain. Completing the supply chain for tuna products will help businesses in the chain have stable revenue and profit growth, increase the competitiveness of Vietnamese tuna products in the Japanese market. . Since then, Vietnamese tuna products can easily meet other demanding markets.

Theoretically, there have been many studies on product supply chain, seafood supply chain and tuna supply chain has been mentioned. But there are no systematic and complete studies on the tuna product supply chain and specifically for the Japanese market.

With current fishing development policies of the government, such as: Policies to encourage investment in modernization of fishing vessels, policies to encourage development of community fisheries management models, policies to encourage marine farming (replacing Decision No. 126/2005 / QD-TTg), marine strategy to 2020, investment policy for infrastructure in centralized aquaculture areas, investment policy on control system quality control and management in the fisheries sector These are the factors that facilitate the development of the tuna product supply chain model, to better meet the needs of the market. Japanese market, facilitating access to other difficult markets.

2. Current situation of tuna supply chain to Japan

2.1. Size and price volatility of the Japanese tuna market

Japan is a country surrounded by ocean. The country's seafood industry has been developed for a long time and has greatly contributed to the life of Japanese people, not only economically but also in promoting culture through cuisine.

Japan is world-famous for its tradition of consuming fish and seafood products. Japanese seafood products such as sushi, sashimi, tempura have become popular in the global market due to their health, low fat, and low calorie content. The Japanese seafood market includes finfish, shellfish, edible seaweed, frozen and canned products or other packaged products.

However, the younger generation in Japan has begun to consume less fish and seafood products and instead prefer meat and processed products that are ready to eat. Young consumers with demand for fish and seafood,

they will look to food and drink services with products that are easy to prepare or ready to eat. As a result, whole fish is being replaced by ready-to-eat / fillet forms at retail stores.

Another noteworthy issue is not only the declining consumption of fish and seafood, but the demand for fish-based foods may not come from Japanese consumers in the future. This is due to the growing demand for Japanese cuisine in major markets, especially China, as well as North American and European countries that are experiencing a boom in Japanese cuisine.

Japanese consumers are shifting to cheaper seafood, but still attach great importance to factors such as high quality, freshness, health benefits and food hygiene and safety. The distinctive feature of Japanese consumers is that they value Japanese standards over international standards, such as the "Japan Agricultural Standards" (JAS) or "Industrial Standards. Japan" (JIS - Japan Industrial Standards).

2.2. Japanese market characteristics

As of December 31, 2017, Japan's population was estimated at 127,333,662, a decrease of -264,063 from the previous year's population of 127,615,396. In 2017, the natural population growth rate was negative because the number of births was -314,092 less than the number of deaths. Due to the immigration status, the population increased by 50,029 people. The sex ratio in the total population is 0.955 (955 males per 1,000 females) which is higher than the global sex ratio. The global sex ratio in the world in 2017 was about 1,017 males per 1,000 females. Here are the key figures of the population in Japan in 2017: 1,037,837 children born 1,351,929 dead Increased natural population: -314,092 migrants: 50,029 people 62,201,354 male as of December 31, 2017 65,132,308 female gender as of December 31, 2017 (apdx 10)

In Japan, the natural rate of increase is quite low and tends to decrease gradually. Japan is facing population pressure and the Japanese population tends to age. A large proportion of workers in Japan are approaching retirement age, while the number of replacement workers is decreasing. Although Japan is the country with the highest life expectancy in the world, the birth rate here is low.

Due to geographical factors, Japan is a country associated with mountains and seas, so the main food is marine products, especially marine fish. On the other hand, due to the element of cultural customs, it is very picky in eating. Stemming from the above factors, Japanese people consume 5 times more fish than other countries.

Tuna products are high in Omega 3 -6-9, DHA. The supplement of DHA and Omega 3-6-9 helps in brain development, smarter. Fish is often present in every family meal as well as luxury restaurants. Despite eating a lot of fish, Japanese consumers always know how to schedule each meal, when to eat tuna, and when to eat salmon. ... Especially the Japanese do not abuse too much spices to process food

3. Solutions to improve the efficiency of tuna supply chain to the Japanese market

3.1. Solutions for businesses

a. With fishing business

Faced with a wide range of issues such as declining resources (both reserves and quality), degradation of environmental quality and marine ecosystems, risks from climate change, enforcement of routinely in the process of international integration ... Strengthening the management and reorganizing the form of production for the fleet of ships engaged in offshore fishing activities is now very important. The content mainly focuses on the following issues:

- Manage fishing grounds and uptime of ships, have appropriate solutions for 100% of fishing vessels to comply with regulations on honest record of the master's log, as well as comply with regulations on location control ship and report output. Advocacy should be organized to inform fishermen that they not only have an obligation and responsibility to strictly implement the Fisheries Law, but more importantly, to benefit from compliance with fishing procedures and control of fishing activities. waterfall. In order to ease the traceability and meet the international requirements in catching tuna, so the product price will be higher than before.

- Strictly control all forms of illegal fishing, catch products must conform to and protect rare species, and control costs, revenue and efficiency of offshore fishing activities. .

- Understand the fluctuation of resources, the situation of fish production to adjust the production plan properly.
- Encourage and create favorable conditions for fishermen to organize production in groups, groups of fishing boats, forming service ships to support fishermen in the process of exploiting and transporting tuna to shore.
- Completing policies to support fishermen, creating favorable conditions for fishermen to upgrade fishing means and technical equipment, building new ships with large capacity and configuration suitable to fishing characteristics. Tuna waterfall. In addition, the State also needs to issue regulations on quality standards of offshore fishing vessels and regulations on longevity.
- Designing fishing vessel products must be suitable with fishing characteristics of fishermen, fishing methods, technologies used for exploitation, requirements for post-exploitation products.
- Propagating, disseminating, guiding and creating conditions for fishermen to apply good information on fisheries forecasts, as well as applying Japanese technology in tuna fishing.
- It is necessary to have policies from businesses to attract fishermen to participate in training and develop human resources for marine fishing activities, encourage fishermen's children to participate in training classes, step by step become fishermen have professional qualifications according to standards (such as having diplomas or certificates from vocational schools, technical workers' schools, intermediate schools, or universities ...). There is a roadmap for implementing the regulations on minimum qualifications for offshore operators according to the positions on board. Attracting crew members after labor export on Korean and Taiwan ocean fishing vessels ... to join the domestic ocean fleet.
- To expand the socialization in the training of fishermen, in the immediate future, to concentrate on training the generalization of captains and chief engineers for offshore fishing ships. To adopt a step-by-step policy to attract a workforce with high technical skills, foreign language knowledge and understanding of international law to participate in exploitation, especially cooperation and exploitation in countries and regions. other sea, or fishing operations at international fishing grounds.

Fishing technology (fleet, fishing technology, preservation equipment), skill level of fishermen are decisive to quality, price and competitiveness of seafood products in the market. With the current situation of fishing activities as mentioned above, enhancing product competitiveness in the final consumption stage will face many difficulties. The effects of the input factors affecting the productivity, quality and competitiveness of products on the market are as follows:

Regarding ships, technology to exploit and preserve products

Marine fishing vessels are mostly small ships with wooden hulls, with old apparatus installed on the ship, lack of equipment on board, so the ship's operation is unsafe, the ability to go offshore and long-term operation at sea. institutional; Low ability to keep cold affects product storage on board. The technology of exploiting and preserving products of tuna fishing in Vietnam is outdated, the productivity and quality of other tuna products are low. Awareness and knowledge of people in implementing exploitation, preliminary processing and preservation of products is not high. New technology should be applied to operating ships. In which, not only is the capacity of the exploiting vessel but also needs to focus on designing a suitable fishing boat to increase labor productivity and efficiency, and apply new preservation technology to the exploiting vessel. Since then, ensure the quality of tuna after exploitation right from the moment it is caught on board.

On the other hand, it is also important to pay attention to the types of vessels that share or transport tuna, including:

Co-transshipment - cold cargo ship (logistics ship for cold cargo)

Refrigerated vessels are designed to carry perishable products that require temperature control and therefore require cargo refrigeration. Most reefer vessels are used to carry fish, fruit, vegetables, meat and dairy products, etc. Vessels used to transport fish include live fish and refrigerated vessels. Develop storage technologies for ships with deeper colds, which will help improve the productivity of offshore tuna vessels. Tuna can be shipped at sea to early consumer countries, ships with deeper refrigeration technology can improve fisheries management, reduce capacity problems and reduce spoilage. product due to loss of temperature control.

Container ships with refrigeration equipment: (Reefer carrier)

Reefer container ships carrying cargo containers with refrigeration equipment. The invention of reefer containers allowed perishable products to be transported to remote locations while maintaining the original quality of the product. Function-wise, reefer container ships can be classified as standard refrigerated container ships, gas controlled container ships, ultra-low temperature reefer container ships and ultra-low temperature cargo container ships. Container vessels that can be refrigerated at extremely low temperatures can export tuna to Japan for the demand for sashimi products at extremely low temperatures - 60 ° C. For colder container ships - 25 ° C and above - 35 ° C, it is possible to transport tuna for canning or to accommodate tuna sashimi products. Tuna products have high economic value, especially sashimi products, so temperature issues must be closely monitored so as not to adversely affect all frozen sashimi products. Requires a container vessel or shipping company to regularly conduct random checks of the fish's temperature, to ensure the tuna has reached extremely low temperatures according to the standards, to avoid the possibility of adverse effects of temperature on the product. .

In contrast, reefer container ships will provide low transportation costs, no cost of fuel and international control. Although aircraft are frequently used by businesses to carry tuna products, in the context of the international environment, transportation costs, fuel costs and the need for international control Increasingly, it can be seen as a reefer container system as a solution that can reduce costs and efficiency in supplying tuna products to the Japanese market.

e. Relationships and forms of production organization

For tuna fishing fleets in general, about 40% of ships operate in a group model. However, the linkage is quite loose, only supporting each other with weather information, fishing grounds, support when facing natural disasters and enemy sabotage. Lack of economic linkages such as: supporting the transportation of products to the shore, supporting the transportation of fuel and food to prolong the time of sea clinging. Therefore, to increase the cohesion of the tuna fishing fleet, it is necessary to pay attention to the following activities:

Logistics operations, service and other support

Fishing ports, fishing wharves: To complete the logistics service system, including fishing ports and fishing ports, which need to be improved in terms of infrastructure and services for fishing vessels. Improved channel system to help fishing vessels easily in and out of the port. Establishing purchasing establishments to ensure food hygiene and safety and environmental sanitation conditions.

Shipbuilding and repairing establishments: Forming shipbuilding establishments with large scale, applying technology to repairing and renovating ships, attaching modern repair service establishments near fishing ports. Form a chain of continuous services to meet the needs of tuna fishing.

Fisheries Forecasting: The forecasting work of tuna fishing ground has been done in recent years; perfect forecasting methods, improve the quality of forecasts for fishing grounds, close to the actual situation. Strengthen information channels that can be used by fishermen, but must also ensure easy to use and timely processing of information, avoiding the occurrence of information delays or errors.

Strengthening the fishing logistic service fleet: In order to reduce the time for tuna to be brought ashore, Binh Dinh - Phu Yen - Khanh Hoa provinces are now organizing the model of a cooperative team at sea. has reduced transit time. However, with limited quantity, as well as investment in the logistics model, there is no specialization in the logistics model, both fast transportation of products after mining to the shore, and investment in refrigeration technology to Product quality maintenance is still limited. Therefore, it is necessary to form a fleet of specialized logistics services, including supplying essential goods, raw materials - fuels, medical equipment, and carrying out product-to-door services with standard tunneling. Best product refrigerant. From there, improving the quality of tuna right from the start, reducing the rate of post-harvest losses, increasing the output of sashimi and other processed products of high quality for the Japanese market. Copy.

b. Solutions for export processing enterprises

To improve the source of goods and quality of tuna and tuna products. In the coming time, businesses should focus on organizing training, improving the professionalism of procurement staff, limiting the purchase and sale through intermediaries to reduce costs and reduce costs. owner of the source. Domestic raw materials need to establish raw material gathering stations to directly purchase raw materials, at the same time, it is necessary to study and implement a project of collecting and storing products at a temperature of -25 0C to collect sources. materials, quality assurance of tuna and tuna products exported to Japan. Since then, tuna products of Vietnam can achieve high value when exporting and compete with tuna products of other countries in the Japanese market.

- For foreign suppliers

It is necessary to maintain a strategic relationship with key suppliers, and constantly seek new suppliers to minimize dependence on some existing suppliers. Especially for tuna products as input materials for factories that process and produce processed tuna products. Expansion of supply from many different suppliers is essential to avoid price pressure, offset input materials for the production of processed tuna products.

- For domestic suppliers

Maintain and develop good relations with domestic suppliers. In the immediate future, it is necessary to organize guidance to local owners on the procedures for purchasing, preserving and transporting raw materials, making records related to the traceability records. and ensure standards of hygiene - food safety. Also point out the benefits to these owners from these activities. If the required processes are met and ensured, the proportion of tuna that meets the standards for processed products will increase, reducing the amount of goods that must be imported from outside suppliers, the price of tuna will increase. reached a higher level than the previous traditional method.

It is necessary to focus on improving the quality of goods, increasing labor productivity through increasing the purchase of high quality raw materials, controlling histamine content in raw materials, upgrading production conditions: factories, equipment, technology, tools, tools ... to ensure that raw materials for the factory are preserved or put into production immediately, produced goods are not stagnant for long, affecting product quality. Raising awareness and professional qualifications for each employee in the production process, improving labor productivity.

The current categories of tuna exports from Vietnam include: whole fresh tuna, frozen whole, frozen processed, frozen steamed, canned tuna ...

The factory processing tuna products for export needs to be equipped with advanced processing machines, equipment and tools to ensure the conditions of processing technology and food safety and hygiene. In which, it is necessary to implement a quality management program according to HACCP. The factories that want to enter the Japanese market must equip a laboratory system to control product quality, especially microbiological and

histamine parameters. Physical and chemical standards, sensory standards, packaging standards and labels of tuna products supplied by Vietnam must conform to the standards of the Japanese market.

In order to minimize the risk of fluctuations in customer demand, it is necessary to promote marketing strategies, introduce products through fairs, use online applications to promote products, learn and evaluate customer need. Enhance the search for more qualified and reputable distributors in the supply of food products, especially for businesses with large retail systems. The partners in the Japanese market have good information sharing ability, and can assist chain members to meet the Japanese requirements for tuna products.

It is necessary to diversify products towards more convenience for consumers, establish a branch in Japan to directly introduce products, and introduce tuna products under Vietnamese brands' brands. retail market in Japan.

It is necessary to increase the search for new logistics service providers, capable of providing means of transport and storage to meet the requirements for product quality. Logistics service providers must not only meet the requirements of the transport of goods, but also must meet the requirements of the cold chain. Ability to control and store products at the best temperature. Not only that, expanding the scope of searching for suppliers of packaging and materials in production. From there, reducing costs related to logistics activities, costs related to packaging, meeting the requirements for quality and packaging of the Japanese market.

To support horizontal linkage for sustainable development, the reorganization of production and establishment of cooperative groups (groups, cooperatives) according to Decree 151/2007 / ND-CP, Draft of Organization and Operation Action of the cooperative group - 2017 / ND-CP of the Government is a measure that has a positive impact on the sustainable development of agriculture and rural areas. It is important to promote horizontal linkage: Establishing and operating a cooperative group must come from the needs of the people and joining a cooperative group has to bring economic benefits to each household, thus the operation of the the new partnership can be sustainable. At the same time, the supply of raw materials to the processing factories is also stable in both quality and quantity. Increasing competitiveness for Vietnamese seafood products.

To promote vertical linkage in production development, to encourage consumption of products through contracts. To promote linkages in the chain, processors need to be fully aware of the nuclear role in their chain in order to entice all parties to participate in their value chain activities. Relationships (vertical linkages) must be legally binding (through economic contracts, focusing on setting up long-term contracts) to gradually erase spontaneous production thinking, chase after the virtual market. Strengthening horizontal linkage, working really effectively for the goal of effective and sustainable development of the business, in which attention should be paid to the interests of the nation and the nation (participating in responsible activities in professional associations, commodity associations ...).

Each country, like it or not, has an existing brand, meaning that a number of impressions have been shaped in the minds of the public in general and consumers in particular, to influence the shopping behavior of surname.

The promotion of product consumption results from a dialectical consequence between the three entities that are national brands, corporate brands and product brands. The same product brand, according to the same standards of the manufacturer, but produced in different countries, product recognition is also different. Commitment, implementation of product quality standards, environmental protection certified by independent organizations such as MSC ecolabel or certification of the production process of head product HACCP, ISO 22000 ... Meeting the requirements of import markets, creating Vietnamese products to penetrate the Japanese market. Along with that, businesses have increased promotional activities in the Japanese market. In particular, focus on tools such as: Advertising, promotion in the distribution channel, participating in fairs - exhibitions - product introduction, Online marketing for tuna products of Vietnam. .

To ensure the competitiveness of Vietnamese seafood products that are accepted and trusted by the market, or in other words so that consumers can really believe in tuna products under the brand "made in Vietnam", product quality must be on top. In recent years, the preservation of products to reduce post-harvest losses in Vietnam has been very concerned. However, post-capture losses in Vietnam are still high. The output product quality is also not stable. Tuna is no exception. Therefore, it is necessary to apply new technologies in exploitation, change production and exploitation methods; strengthen coordination of ship operators, logistics services, processing enterprises, state management agencies. Implement quality control right from the start, tighten records of captains during tuna fishing, establish service businesses responsible for supplying raw materials in tuna preservation. positive.

As the nucleus, dominating the supply chain, being the pioneer force to bring fishing products to the table of the domestic market as well as for export, the enterprise will be the one who requests the supplier (fishermen) supply products according to market-appropriate standards. In fact, the longer the supply chain, the lower the uniformity of quality while the higher the cost. The fact that businesses directly sign product consumption contracts will contribute to changing fishermen's perceptions of improving product quality, meeting market requirements. The most important thing is that the fishermen's income is increased if middlemen are reduced.

In addition, businesses also need to participate directly in the market through the auctions of fishing products, providing information to operators, transparency of the market (transparency of prices, costs of the chain, quality standards for tuna, responsibility of chain actors), promoting production development through continuous investment in processing, product diversification and quality enhancement amount.

3.2. Recommendations to the State

From now to 2025, a new approach to state management is needed. In the context of deep integration, increasing competition, tight trade agreements will make State management resources difficult to apply flexibly, in accordance with the circumstances. reality. In terms of improving the quality of offshore fishing, the State needs to create a strong enough investment policy mechanism to create a driving force to bring investment flows from businesses and fishermen into the current deficient sector such as building new fishing ships, encouraging enterprises to participate in providing services at sea.

The State also needs to encourage the expansion of forms of horizontal linkage between businesses such as the establishment of professional associations and associations, so that from the commitment to building the image and brand of the enterprise towards the formation of a brand. National Brand. Also supporting fishing, but near-shore fishing requires investment resources to focus on fleets with tuna fishing technology or technology to preserve fresh, clean products, which will bring high efficiency. for fishermen.

The State needs to support vocational training for fishermen, provide credit capital through many channels, simple loan procedures so that they can expand investment in machinery and equipment, expand production activities.

a. Activities of Science, technology and extension

The investment for research, application, transfer, and extension is low. Strengthen the contingent of science and technology with high professional qualifications. To put research into and apply new technologies to the operation of exploitation, preservation, processing, transportation, management and information systems of the tuna product supply chain.

b. International cooperation

International cooperation with governments and with other countries and regional and international fisheries management organizations, with NGOs on environmental protection, protection of endangered species of

interest and active deployment. Actively participate in the prevention, prevention and elimination of illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing activities. However, this is both an opportunity and a challenge:

- Building a brand, image of a responsible country. In addition, Vietnam has also enlisted the support of experience, scientific and technological knowledge in the exploitation and protection of aquatic resources in general and tuna resources in particular. Finally, tuna products will have the opportunity to penetrate deeply into the world market, the fishing grounds can be expanded to the waters of other countries and international waters;
- Trade barriers of importing countries are increasingly high for aquatic products in general and tuna products in particular. Therefore. It is necessary to perform well the close linkage in the supply chain in order to fulfill product requirements. To do this, it is necessary to focus on the first activity in the supply chain of tuna products, which is fishing activities, then transport, preservation and processing activities. Accompanying it is the transfer of technology to increase productivity and product quality of the supply chain. Expanding cooperation with countries with developed tuna fisheries is one of the urgent requirements, helping Vietnam quickly access and meet the requirements of exploitation, processing and export. tuna products.

c. Build an image of Vietnam as a responsible fisheries nation

It is clear that Vietnam is a responsible country in the effective and sustainable management of fishing activities, accompanied by social security step by step improving the material and spiritual life of fishermen community, especially fishermen. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development has developed and submitted to the Government for promulgation, and organize and implement the Fisheries Law and regulations on the protection and development of aquatic resources. Continue updating, amending, supplementing and completing the system of legal documents as a basis for improving the efficiency of sector management. For the system of documents on exploitation and protection of aquatic resources to really promote efficiency and come to life.

d. Increase access to capital for chain members

Raising the maximum level of unsecured loans of some customers who are individuals, households to 2 times the old maximum loan. Helping fishermen to exploit tuna, businesses can access better capital in investing in means and technology for exploitation and processing to meet the market's product quality standards.

Implementing reduced lending procedures and time for low capital needs, meeting the need to buy raw materials for shipping by fishermen, should be resolved within the day. Thereby reducing the costs of capital, increasing the income for the operators.

Should use the model, mobilize social and professional organizations: the government at the social level, the farmers' society, the Women's Union, the Fatherland Front ... to participate as a loan agent of the Bank, especially the where there are no branches of banks in operation.

e) It is necessary to strengthen international cooperation and develop ocean fishing

+ Coordinate with international organizations WCPFC, FAO, APFIC, SEAPDEC to improve capacity of tuna resource management system in Vietnam; Work with international fisheries organizations and other countries to bring some Vietnamese fishing vessels qualified to exploit in common waters and Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of countries. other; and Cooperate with WCPFC, FAO, SEAFDEC and other international organizations to carry out research, resource assessment, and information collection programs for tuna resources management in Vietnam seas and areas. neighborhood.

+ Take the necessary steps to join regional and international fisheries management organizations, such as the Central and Western Pacific Fisheries Commission (WCPFC), to ensure Vietnamese tuna products can penetrating into markets in general and Japan in particular. At the same time, Vietnamese fishing vessels can also participate in fishing in waters under the management of this organization.

3.3. Recommendations to the Association

a. Promote international cooperation and promote promotion of fisheries activities

Processing enterprises accompany and support fishermen to participate in fishing in sea areas in countries that have bilateral fisheries agreements or jointly negotiate and sign bilateral fisheries agreements. with ASEAN countries. Gradually improve the corporate governance system to meet the conditions so that when Vietnam participates in international agreements such as the Agreement on migratory fish stocks, the Agreement on measures of port countries, joins the Groups. the regional fisheries management organization, which is primarily the Midwest Pacific Fisheries Organization (WCPFC) or the bilateral trade agreements FTA,

Well implementing the program "Seafood enterprises committed to combating IUU fishing", applying information technology "CATCH" in checking the origin of fishery products, CATCH will support member countries in their due diligence, which involves illegal mining, helps reduce fraud risks, facilitates trade flows, and reduces the burden on regulators.

b. Business support, suggestions and legal policy recommendations

The above function has been assumed from the beginning by the Association as a regular administrative activity. Since its establishment, the Association has regularly gathered its members' opinions and aspirations, proposals and recommendations to the Prime Minister, the Ministry of Fisheries, the Ministry of Trade, the General Department of Customs, VCCI and a number of other agencies, proposed solutions to develop seafood production in general and tuna products of Vietnam in particular, to reduce troubles for businesses.

The Association has commented on or participated in reviewing many draft Laws, regulations and circulars guiding the need to remove various contents related to the exploitation, processing and export of tuna products. , making operations of businesses less difficult, especially the following issues: increasing costs, reducing competitiveness; causing troubles, hindering the operation of enterprises; affect the rights, interests, obligations of employees and employers....

Strengthening the current relations of the Association with state management agencies, communities, industry associations and related research agencies, and relations between businesses and actors in the supply chain. , foreign customers, international organizations. The Association's comments, criticisms and proposals should aim to demonstrate position, responsibility to the community and society, ensure the sustainable development of the industry and contribute to the improvement of a better business environment. .

4. CONCLUSION

The theory of supply chain development in general has been around since the early 80s of the 20th century. Over the past four decades, supply chain theory has been applied in many areas of the commodity and translation business. service and conditions in different economies. In the fishery products business, the driving forces behind the adoption of supply chain theory include concerns about food safety, child labor and environmental sustainability as well as increased expectations. yield and crop quality improvement ...

In fact in Vietnam, the application of supply chain theory has also been mentioned quite a lot in recent times. However, the benefits brought about by the supply chain to businesses are not really clear. Most Vietnamese businesses have not yet really participated in the process of forming and developing product supply chains. This restriction is related to many factors both from an economic perspective and from an enterprise perspective.

In the process of researching the thesis topic "The solution to complete the supply chain of tuna products for the Japanese market", the graduate student approached from the theory of product supply chain development to analyze , assessing the current situation of the development of the tuna product supply chain and the factors affecting the development of Vietnam's tuna product supply chain. Since then, to complete the supply chain of tuna products for the Japanese market, the thesis has drawn some of the following conclusions:

- (1) The supply chain of tuna products from Vietnam to the Japanese market is not closely linked. Should use forms of long-term contracts, better information sharing among chain members, implementing market transparency is also a good measure to increase linkages among members.
- (2) Must change to mining through the application of new technology in this activity. Along with that are labor training activities, transferring new tuna fishing methods to increase productivity and ensure product quality.
- (3) Form a cold chain, helping to improve product preservation from extraction to post-processing. Parameters of products and materials for preservation are controlled, thereby ensuring and maintaining product quality at a high level.
- (4) Strengthening and improving the quality of fishery logistics, especially logistics services at sea, at fishing ports and other support services.
- (5) Reducing post-harvest losses, improving product quality through the application of new technologies in the chain: extraction technology, preservation technology, processing technology, information technology. Since then, Vietnamese tuna products meet the requirements of traceability.
- (6) Enhance responsibility for the role of tuna processing and exporting enterprises in the chain. Due to capturing market information, having close linkage with importers are the prerequisites for these enterprises to play the leading role of the chain.
- (7) The development of the supply chain will help increase the competitiveness of Vietnam's tuna products to penetrate and expand markets in countries with strict standards for food products in general. and tuna products in particular.
- (8) For state management agencies, it is necessary to have better support policies for the supply chain of tuna products. In particular, it is necessary to focus on developing a large-capacity fleet, perfecting the seaport system, a good credit policy for fishermen and businesses, supporting activities to promote market expansion, construction branding for tuna products of Vietnam.
- (9) For the Association, it is necessary to strengthen the linkage between the Association and its members, between the Association and the state management agency. From there, support for chain members in resource training, technology application in the chain, promotion activities, and proposing recommendations to state management agencies.

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